

Article

Telecommunications End-User Satisfaction Impact on Enterprises Success of Internet Service in Egypt

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Abstract: This research aims to investigate the relationships among End-User Satisfaction “EUS” and the success of Asymmetric digital subscriber lines as an Internet service of enterprises being distributed through internet service providers “ISPs” in Egypt. It is necessary to recognize the EUS dynamism impact on telecommunication enterprises that related to success. For achieving the objectives of this study, an online questionnaire was carried out on well-known Egyptian five enterprises' employee including the owners or/ managers' responders” WOAM”, on the other hand, of ADSL end-users at the regional field. The research result gleaned through quantitative questioner that was tested by using statistical descriptive analyses. The implication study assumed major challenges, which likely to be influenced by the ADSL enterprises success in Egypt, which is end-user satisfaction on success factor. Concerning the ADSL Internet service nature as a high-tech ad-hoc industry that might be obsolete soon in favour of new innovation. Virtually, the selected independent variable may significantly explain the interdependence with the dependent variable. Recommendations, to operators of Telecommunication enterprises and suggestions for interested researchers, are forwarded.

Keywords: Telecommunication enterprises; Internet service providers (ISPs); Internet service (ADSL); End-User Satisfaction (EUS); Success

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Public Interest Statement

End-user satisfaction and introducing a high quality of ADSL Internet service are so germane to interests of economic development and an improved quality of business to meet customer predictions in a diverse range of the home users, corporate deals, and many other activities in operational use. The Internet industry is gaining significant sophistication to provide end-users with more bandwidth to improve their predictions about the internet provider since time means money. However, the relationship between Internet industry effort and EUS is far from obvious. Managing customer, satisfaction, and loyalty attitudes of ADSL Telecommunication enterprises business is a hub for the long-term growth of many businesses.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

In developing countries, the private sector has been instrumental in bringing about the economic transition to tool up the ideal environment to exercise optimally successful economies, assistance and support to strengthen these enterprises can lead to higher profits and employment levels. (Sievers & Vandenberg, 2007:1341). Telecommunication track of providing ADSL Internet service has been undertaken at this paper referring to the internet era. It is being entrusted with ADSL as the most famous Internet service format in Egypt, in this paper, which is the pertinence of Internet fixed-line assets.

A few Egyptian providers have licenses to supply ADSL for end-user directly in different governorates. Specifically, Internet users are counted 31.767 million subscribers considered 35.9% of the population (July 2015 EST.). That means the range comparison occupies the fifteenth out of the world (<https://www.cia.gov/index.html>).

1.2 Problem Statement

End-user satisfaction and introducing a high quality of ADSL Internet service are so germane to interests of economic development and an improved quality of business to meet customer predictions in a diverse range of the home users, corporate deals, and many other activities in operational use. The Internet industry is gaining significant sophistication to provide end-users with more bandwidth to improve their predictions about the internet provider since time means money. However, the relationship between Internet industry effort and EUS is far from obvious. Managing customer, satisfaction, and loyalty attitudes of ADSL Telecommunication enterprises business is a hub for the long-term growth of many businesses. Besides, Telecommunication enterprises do not conduct market research and develop/design a product or service as per the need of customers (Zelege Worku, 2009). EUS impacting telecommunication enterprises success through a comprehensive review of the works of literature and available empirical studies. This resulted in the development of a theoretical framework for the initiation of policies and programs for enterprise development. From the practical point of view, it serves not only to provide a self-check to the current enterprises' sector, even so, further to increase the involvement in business activities through a better understanding of the determinants of the telecommunication enterprises.

1.3 Literature Review

The Arab Republic of consists of approximately 97.55 million in 2017 people. Communication; Telephones; fixed lines service as the main ADSL signal conveyed reported in total subscriptions 6,235,133 subscriptions per 100 inhabitants: 7 (July 2015 est.). Egypt comparison to the world stated is 26th the close relationship between service providers and consumers and the prodigious flexibility of services associated with ICTs lead to an intense process of customization and to a myriad relevance of interactivity (Miles, 2005). The appearance of the ICT-based technological paradigm is hocked with the creation of new advanced service activities, and the co-evolution between the latter and the diffusion of the ICT-based general purpose technologies constitutes a major source of structural change in the knowledge-based economy. Egyptian Internet users counted 37,122,537 million subscribers considered 39.2% of the population (July 2016 EST.) means the range comparison occupies the fifteenth out of the world. (<https://www.cia.gov/index.html>).

1.3.1 Internet Service Telecommunication enterprises Characteristics

Businesses and geographical areas at different socio-economic levels with regard to both their occasions to access information and communication technology and to their use of the Internet for a variety of activities" (T Hüsing; 2002).), whereas the impact of the Internet on competency development and organizational learning has already been studied in the Telecommunication enterprises environment (i.e. Brian R. Webb, Frank Schlemmer, (2008). Individuals who are "connected" and those who remain "disconnected" are a result of evolution from the concept of socio-economic phenomenon. (Norris, 2001). Integration on Internet usage is evidently seen in large

companies, and Telecommunication enterprises occurred. While, ISPs inattentive, in particular, in afar regions

1.3.2.1 Internet Service Providers (ISPs) In Egypt.

ICT sector has been one of the hastiest growing industries in Egypt, with its growth rate exceeding 20 percent annually between 2003 and 2008. Thereby, its contribution to the country's total GDP more than to almost 4 percent in 2008 (Helmy: 2009). Intangibility, inseparability, heterogeneity, durability, perishability, customizations versus standardization debates make them prime candidates to employees ICTs such the Internet service delivery (De-kare Silver, 2000).

In 2000, Broadband Internet access was introduced commercially to Egypt such an ADSL service. The service was offered in select central offices in big cities such as Cairo and Alexandria and gradually spread to cover more Governorates of Egypt. In 2003, The National Telecommunications Regulatory Authority (NTRA) was established in accordance with the provision of Law No. 10, for the year 2003 to enhance, regulate as well as achieve industry stability, EUS, and state welfare. The largest ISP in Egypt was LINKdotNET, the majority shares of which are owned by Orascom Telecom. A merger between Egypt's first and largest two ISPs, Link-Egypt and IN-Touch Communications.

In 2005, LINKdotNET had about 250,000 subscribers, served by some 300 professionals. (Taking the E-train, Rasha Abdulla: 2005).

Seven companies owned the infrastructure, and they are called class (A) ISPs: (Egynet, LINKdotNET, TE Data, NOL, Vodafone data, Noor communication and Yalla). Etisalat MISR has bought both NileOnline and Egynet to expand their Internet presence. They sell to class (B) ISPs. Which, in turn, sell to the rest of the 208 ISPs.

In 2009, Orange Telecom (the commercial brand of France Telecom) dominated telecom foreign investment to make ownership of Internet service Telecommunication enterprises more convoluted, Mobinil Telecom is owned partially by Orascom Telecom (28.75 percent) and the French Telecom Group through Orange, which owns the remaining shares (71.25 percent) (Michael J. Oghia: 2011). Gathering Mobinil as an Egypt's second largest mobile service operator and LINKdotNET under Orascom Telecom group, By Orange it had been bought out as well as It expected to be completed taking over within the first quarter of 2015.

In 2016, Telecom Egypt (TE Data) sized 76% of ADSL market share and reached 573 thousand subscribers during 2016 to peaked the highest number of ADSL subscribers with 2.2 million subscribers overall. Egypt's major fixed broadband providers become TE Data with fixed-line infrastructure monopoly recognition. Otherwise, Vodafone, Orange, and Etisalat are leased capacity from it.

Recently, the government has an 80% share in TE Data. In August 2016, TE Data received the country's first unified services license, allowing it to offer LTE, fixed-line, mobile voice and data services. Other providers initially rejected the terms, although all three have since received licenses.

Table 1. Internet improvement during last ten years.

Egypt's internet profile	2006	2016
Number of Internet users	5.2 million	29.84 million
Users' annual growth rate	500% (2002-2005)	16.1% (2012-2016)
Bandwidth	5.355 Gbps	1136.81 Gbps
Number of ISPs	300	208
Registered IT clubs	1024	77

Source: Ministry of Communications and Information Technology (MCIT, 2006, 2017).

Broadband connections in Egypt vary in quality. The quality depends on the distance from the central loop office, the presence of the ISP in that local loop, and the quality of the copper telephone line on which the broadband connection is carried. Internationally, Egypt is currently served with three international submarine cables. Namely, with the announcement of Telecom Egypt owned cable TENorth and Orascom telecom owned MENA. Ideas to improve the elasticity of international

broadband. In high-velocity markets, examples of successful implementations are rare. The way in which Telecommunication enterprises collaborated and co-evolved in the creation and development of the ISP industry is one example but even here Internet service industry soon came to be dominated by fewer grander ISPs, with the result that routines became more established, outcomes more predictable and capabilities less dynamic (Austin, 2002). Forecast of Austin has been occurred and nor is change limited for the ISPs point of view nonetheless, a great transformation to fiber optics occurred since 2013 until now in vast regional sections in Egypt, further for Telecommunication enterprises readiness capability in Egyptian ADSL Internet service.

1.3.2.2 Internet Service telecommunication enterprises' Model.

In the economics literature, a traditional and eminent distinction is the one between producer, distributive and personal services (Gershuny and Miles, 1983; Park and Chan, 1989). This simple taxonomy is not explicitly focused on innovation. Nonetheless, it is imperative because it points out the different function that diverse groups of service sectors perform within the economic system, i.e. as providers of intermediate/distributive or final services respectively. Primarily used in the sales force automation and dominated customer-management relationships, service producers/distributor that now widely applied in sales channels of management, computerized billing, service desk management, pre-paid client-systems, human-resource management, and others of various business's processes (Biddick, 2010). No complicated hardware or software is needed, and high-priced licenses are evaded since the service is used on demand, either through a time subscription model (Reuwer, T., Jansen, S., and Brinkemper, S., 2013).

ADSL as an Internet service as long as potential end-users are encouraged to deal with, legally, due to the exhibited low-price compare with the leased line's costly price or back to back Internet service system. Sharing concept is a prime element of ADSL usage from both provider and user. Technically, the end user consumes the ADSL service with other shared subscribers at the same time yielding a reasonable price. The internet traffic seems to be congested and other times result in delighted subscribers pertaining to the ADSL ISP sharing concept of "moral and justice". Virtually, ISPs could not reach to whole potential clients even though the advertisement campaign, marketing promotion, the shareholders' stress. Therefore, the distribution comes up the main milestone in current era whether off/online marketing performed. Each salesman is asked to forecast sales in his territory (McAfee, 1987). Salesman effort in the realm of online space causes the fame of ADSL Telecommunication enterprises depending on after-sale creditability. "Word of mouth "usage convinces current users, entice potential customers and unplanned clients. Thus, the acquaintance's connection and fast customer service are superior in favor ADSL Telecommunication enterprises, typically, in case the Internet line cut off. Distributors of Internet service Telecommunication enterprises treat with a preferable way rather than large ISPs companies, due to a rat movement, not such ISPs' elephant reaction. Collecting Internet service's fees out of abandoned regions through a reseller or/and an agent is proper, quicker and safer. Especially whenever security's absence, obsolete infrastructure, and distant distances are noticed in ADSL service region case. Customer service collected fees and salesmen efforts are mostly the needs of ISPs' giants and that simply what Internet service Telecommunication enterprises distribution is involved in.

1.3.2.3 Structure of internet service Telecommunication Enterprises

When interdependence is low and there is a little need for worker cooperation as, for example, in field sales and call centers work can be designed for individual jobs. Obtaining sufficient sales is a challenge, in particular, for smaller firms (Hall & Young 1991).

Figure 1. Organization structure levels of ADSL Telecommunication enterprises

As illustrated figure shown there are common, three levels in ADSL Telecommunication enterprises, first, chief duty level represents the ownership, human resource, and financing management in particular. Inspire the subordinates to go beyond their abilities for providing a reasonable service or a better way of completing their tasks (Millissa F.Y. Cheung: 2010). Second, supervision level accounted for. In other words, the mediate level, which controls performing the WOAM perspective, goals, conveying “emotionally” up-down daily transactions. Employee satisfaction with their supervisor can lower employees’ withdrawal cognitions, and that the way employees were treated by their supervisors has a powerful effect on employee performance and retention (Aquino, K., Griffeth, R. W., Allen, D. G., & Hom, P. W. (1997). Third, employee level, overwhelm/discerning success would be depended on creativity, maturity, taking responsibility and professionally of direct user treated level. The significance of service employee creativity requires us to establish a systematic understanding of comprehensive processes, including its antecedents and consequences (Inyong Shin, Won-Moo Hur, and Hongseok Oh: 2015). On other word, understandings, adopting, implementing Telecommunication enterprises tasks are limited by the accomplishment of the first level who deals with the ADSL end-user and signifies the Telecommunication enterprises image.

1.3.3 Concept of Success’s internal factors

Telecommunication enterprises success is closely linked to service enterprises performance. Success in business is a matter of opinion and may be related to the degree to which objectives are met or exceeded, some of which may be critical for success (Claire O’donovan et al., 2003) equate success with high performance.

1.3.3.1 Definition of success

Recognition of success is a prime concern of business researchers. However, some of them have gotten resemblance methodological findings and the others dealing with profit only they are quite far from our study’s authenticity. As follows follow some of the Internet service Telecommunication enterprises definitions.

- Success is defined such “the sustained satisfaction of principal stakeholder aspirations” Jennings and Beaver (1997) and contend that success could “no longer regarded as synonymous with optimum performance, From this perspective, successful Telecommunication enterprises while failing to achieve the ideal level of performance in terms of growth and business development.

- Defining success is reinforced in the context of Internet service Telecommunication enterprises, reflecting the combination of financial and non-financial meanings being pursued. However, non-financial are being more concerned.
- Defined success has been continuing of business traffic and disappointment confronts trading cease rather. Nevertheless, this is too one-dimensional since Telecommunication enterprises cease to trade for a variety of reasons other than financial failure (Stokes and Blackburn, 2002).
- Success in terms of growth (Perren, 2000; O'Gorman, 2001) or profitability, while the implication of substitutes to growth and profit are recognized within the literature, less attention has been placed on the satisfaction behavior of Telecommunication enterprises owners or/and managers, which may be eager to adjust their objectives in order to remain running their business. Nonetheless, then again, this standpoint is problematic in the context of Internet service Telecommunication enterprises where an assortment of goals being pursued.

1.3.3.2 Maintain after-sale customer services

Worthy customer relationships and customer service have been found to be the most essential factor contributing to SME success (Wijewardena & Cooray 1996). In his study of high-tech firms, Räsänen (1999) exposed the position of close customer relationships (also Halborg et al. 1997). Telecommunication enterprises contributed in a lot in the form of help to get surviving during a global recession. To offer exceptional customer services, i.e. sending out regular personal e-mails dealing special offers, taking steps to ensure service delivery is effective, offering flexible payment terms. Moreover, when coordinated activity is directed at customer service, it can assure customers that their interests will be considered and satisfied during the merger. Process-based structures is growing rapidly in a variety of service companies. The longer-term and more difficult parts of implementation, however, involve changes in the organization's support systems, such as customer service. Culture Change at IBM of the basic value is "the best customer service," (Fortune, March 31, 2003). Telecommunication enterprises management in internet service customer service should be cognizant that "era of the telephone has been transited to the era of the smartphone", aware that handling of the client has become more focused than before.

The front line service desk needs the right information in the right place and time to serve the users, they could not work blindly. Providing regular precise information reduce workload and raise up staff relief to serve the users in a supreme way. It appears that increasing overall service quality will contribute to a higher appraisal of EUS. Hence, in assessing satisfaction with broadband access, consumers are likely to consider both customer service features (i.e., employee's professionals, attitude and interesting) and ADSL features (i.e. speed browsing, downloads ability, transmission quality, and stability).

1.3.4 Customer Satisfaction Conceptualization

The concept of Satisfaction can be acknowledged in several sounds depending on what needs the customer had before the service; it arrays from feelings of fulfilment, contentment, preference, enjoyment, relief, and ambivalence, loyalty and retention can integrate with other perspectives as a conceptualization of service dynamics (Harris and Goode, 2004), Zekiri and Angelova (2011) who shapes that: "Customer satisfaction does have a positive effect on an organization's profitability", Maximizing ROI would be an acceptable strategy to culminate customer satisfaction (Rechheld and schefter (2000)).

Attempt to understand possible positive consequences of lower-attentive service, this paper draws on the concepts of reactance exhibited by employee and internet users to identify and subsequently test.

The author conceded many valuable merits of customer satisfaction within conceptual pluralism approaches to proof the position of customer satisfaction factor generally and Internet services Telecommunication enterprises in particular. Retaining customer with the highest potential value that attracting the topical ADSL subscribers. Profitability, chosen strategy, market share, total quality management are focused on other customer satisfaction findings as a mutual factor leads to

a different point of views. Identically, factorize the EUS to be endured by interacted internal factors of Telecommunication enterprises, further, impacting Internet service Telecommunication enterprises success is pointed out in this research.

1.3.4.1 Perception of customer satisfaction

- Customer satisfaction is complex construct and has been defined in various approaches, recently; it has been argued that there is a distinction between customer satisfaction as related to intangibility service experiences and perishability of services. Researching customer satisfaction in services whether satisfaction is conceptualized as facet "user attribution" or as overall "practice accumulation"; and whether it is viewed as transaction-specific "win-win situation" or as ultimate impression "last-minute influence" (Høst, V., & Knie-Andersen, M. (2004). ADSL Telecommunication enterprises EUS is seen as a mission of pre-existing expectations and contractual prospect as regard to the user's perfect gaze for issues around life and contrast of qualification of user's level.
- Customer expectation performance; that leads to is considered as a pre-request to keeping harmonious working connotation (Soetanto et al, 2001). That presented formulae for quality, quality under expectation is more beneficial (karana et al 2009). That expectation always comes from different values of customer experience. This extends to the gap between customers' expectations of service and their perception of the service experiences Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V. A., & Berry, L. L. (1985).
- Customer experiences; impact should be anticipating and fulfilling customer needs, better than competitors through providing real know-how consumption, bestowing genuine emotional experience services, generate customer experience that was beyond physical attributes such as quality, delivery, price-product bundling, security and privacy (Oswald A. Mascarenhas, Ram Kesavan, Michael Bernacchi, (2006)). Experiences as distinct market offerings, Experiences as interactions arose from the value-adding interactions of customer involvement and provider participation as well as experiences as engaging memories. These experiences engage the customers to create memories within them (Gilmore and Pine, 2002). Compilation elements influenced by customer expectation are grouped, such (word of mouth, price tolerance, personal needs, and prior expectation of similar Internet service distributors). Therefore, focusing to emblemize those factors are so meaningful to boost loyalty, commitment more than EUS. Eventually, the satisfied customer would not necessarily guarantee after-time co-operation with Internet service Telecommunication enterprises. However, undertaking customer loyalty is targeted. Nonetheless, the main aim is promoting client himself by extraordinary satisfaction.
- Customer loyalty; three conceptual perspectives have been suggested to define customer loyalty: the behavioral perspective, the attitudinal perspective and the composite perspective (Zins, 2001). Emphasizing on past -rather than on- future action is the main trait of a user loyalty act. i) Loyal behavioral actions such as price tolerance, word of mouth, or complaint behavior can be interpreted (Ibid). ii) Attitudinal perspective, in contrast, allows gaining in supplemental understanding of loyal behavior (Ibid). Based on a favorable attitude towards a service provider, customers may develop "preference loyalty". iii) Composite perspective might be considered as a substitute to touching loyalty since using both attitude and behavior in a loyalty explanation arguably upturns the predictive power of loyalty (Pritchard and Howard, 1997).
- Customer commitment; there are two types of customer commitment conceptualizations: *Calculative commitment* is the way that the customer is forced to remain loyal to his or her desire (De Ruyter et al., 1998). Feeling ending the relationship involves an economic or social sacrifice (Fullerton, 2005). Effective and calculative or *continuance commitment*, having different antecedents, contents, and consequences (Zins, 2001).

1.3.4.2 EUS affecting ADSL Telecommunication enterprises success.

Little research on the broader aspects of judgmental success factors and the activities involved in ADSL services and means through which the judgmental success factors influence the EUS in

Telecommunication enterprises. Based on EUS, customer retention, competitive advantage, service quality, service management, judgmental success factors and ADSL services, that there is a need for exploring various necessary success factors with associated activities for an ADSL service distributor to follow in order to be contentious and retain the customer. Evidence that by following necessary success factors, there are few expected outcomes to client and service distributor Telecommunication enterprises, like EUS for the client, and competitive advantage and customer retention in ADSL service-distributing Telecommunication enterprises. Three important success factors by which ADSL service distributor can promote EUS in user Telecommunication enterprises: (1) Retain and win customers; (2) improve service management skills; and (3) the Internet its technical support skills. It has been guided by the paper of (Jayachandra Bairi, B. Murali Manohar, (2011).

Critical success factors: Retain and win customers use to be reliable and keep promises, Take ownership of issues. Keep customers informed, if everyone in the team makes a decision now to improve customer contact, magic will happen and problems will reduce. Turn any contact with a customer into something positive. Treat customers the way you like to be treated, Know service level agreement, Develop an ability to listen, Serving the customers deserves a sense of pride. Moreover, achieving communication skills “avoiding Procrastination, Rudeness, Indifference not usually client opinion, supervisor Being invisible for the user” is right, Making promises that can’t be kept, Criticizing your colleagues in public really listen. Improve service management skills. Information exchange, every business study has shown that the way the “internal” information exchange works will always reflect upon the “external” business. Attitude. First impressions Vision.

Figure 2. Critical success factors

On the other hand, Pham, C., Greenwood, J., Cleland, H., Woodruff, P., & Maddern, G. (2007), were observing influenced satisfied customers by further factors, which are staff contentment through the solid managerial business process, that leading to dramatic efficiency. Utilitarian service quality also refers to grateful implementation in a correct way. They proposed the model to classify Critical Success Factors in categories: functional and technical, the components fitting the functional measurement and those having a place within the technical measurement. They are affecting directly the staff satisfaction resulting in high level of users’ satisfaction.

Figure 3. Factor affecting customer satisfactions, Maddern et al., 2007

1.3.4.2.1 Customer service quality

Customer satisfaction is an asset that should be checked and managed just like any physical asset. Service quality has been defined as customers’ comprehensive assessment of service (Ganguli and Roy, 2011).

Telecommunications services dominate the world economy, and their quality is a key factor for generating value for their customers and for society (OECD, 2007). Taylor (1997) pointed out that service quality is a precursor of consumer satisfaction. High perceived service quality results in higher customer satisfaction, and vice versa. It has been recognized that a high quality of service provides benefits, which include: cross-selling opportunities, increased likelihoods of word-of-mouth recommendation, maintenance of positive long-term customer relationships improved corporate image, enhanced customer satisfaction, and decreased customer defection (Dauda, S. Y, Lee, J., & Lee, J. (2016). In spite of quality standards, Telecommunication enterprises may have incentives to decrease quality in order to reduce costs.

Quality of ADSL service represents the degree to which a presence satisfies the user’s needs; as such, quality inclines to play a focal role in the success of the provided service, due to the intangible nature of ADSL services. Some studies tend to view service quality as a major construct in explaining customer satisfaction (Omachonu et al., 2008), while others’ interpretation it in terms of customer loyalty (Aydin, S., & Özer, G. (2005).), customer retention, and other related constructs. Noteworthy, several researchers believe that positive relationship between perceptions of overall service quality and customer satisfaction is attended. (Dauda, S. Y., Dauda, S. Y., Lee, J., & Lee, J. (2016).).

Measuring service quality to give managers key information to generate value for their customers and for society and to estimate whether the quality of utility Telecommunication enterprises is really improving (Bovaird, T., & Löffler, E. (2003). Users are highly subtle to features of service quality and the request’s timeliness’ appreciating, responsiveness, assurance, reliability, and continuity of the telecommunications distribution. These variables are supposed to have an optimistic effect on quality (Bolton and Drew, 1991). It is necessary to define the standards of service quality to avoid the Telecommunication enterprises stop from providing a satisfactory step of quality. Privatization and liberalization can obligate the telecommunication provider to deliver a higher service quality (Pina, V., Torres, L., & Bachiller, P. (2014). In the telecommunications industry, there has been astonishing progress in technology and this has contributed to redesigning service delivery.

Technological advances result in sophisticated network reliability as well as a fundamental determinant of quality as they influence how the Internet service provider is. Infrastructure solely is decisive for engendering growth and increasing service quality. Nevertheless, more experience, preceding practice, and a pricing role have led to a disparity between market segments and, as a result, to better Internet service's access and higher service quality.

1.3.4.2.2 Prior practices

Echeverri and Skålén (2011) understanding practices by emphasizing interaction value, which may be either positive or negative (Based on identical elements). Central to practices is the notion that different actors will experience different realities, basing on the assessor role. theorize the service experience as a process rather than merely an outcome that takes place in an internet service system where there are multiple performers and where the experience is contextually and phenomenologically determined by the individual (Vargo and Lusch, 2008).

Telecommunication enterprises providing service experiences for customers. Here, the highlighting is on the provision of service from the firm to the customer (Janet R McColl-Kennedy, Lilliemay Cheung, Elizabeth Ferrier, (2015)). The focus is on performativity or enactments and communications with others, in other words, shared practices which evolve over time.

Classification of practices

- a) The ways a customer uses consumption objects to classify themselves in relative to others through demonstrating objects group actions, such as when spectators jump up and let out exclamations, or through mentoring activities (McColl-Kennedy et al, 2015).
- b) Puccinelli, N. M., Goodstein, R. C., Grewal, D., Price, R., Raghubir, P., & Stewart, D. (2009), while focused on brand community and not service experience per se, their study highlights the importance of activities and the different ways individuals engage with others.
- c) Kjellberg and Helgesson (2007) they offer a practice-based model of markets.
- d) (Ibid) highlight the "performativity" idiom in markets that direct attention to the emergent and unfolding practices that actors engage in.

1.3.4.2.3 Service's price fairness

To judge the fairness of the price, a user measures the price according to an add-value, the price relative to other prices (those offered by competitors or paid by other customers), and/or the fairness of the price-setting practice.

Customers may view secrecy about pricing practices as another layer of unfairness. Therefore, understanding when to release pricing information and what information to make known is essential to lessening negative consumer response, particularly when pricing in a down economy (Robinson, J. A. (2008)). Conversely, consumers will be afforded an expected price when they trust reflection of higher price upon them. The seller's costs and not an increase in the seller's relative profit levels (Kahneman, D., Knetsch, J. L., & Thaler, R. H. (1986). That the seller's cost increment and price increases are aligned with the service offered (Bolton and Alba, 2006), thus, framing can influence perceptions of price justice. The pricing perspective, procedural fairness (regulation used to determine the price) is an end in itself and not just a means for a result price, as people craving fairness for fairness's sake. Perceived procedural fairness has direct effects on the buyer's responses to prices. The risky feelings associated with intangible services will lead, on average, to more counterfactual thoughts about a better possible outcome with the purchase than the same money spent on a fixed good (Nguyen and Meng, 2013). Therefore, Internet service's price could be a mean of acquisition the user's heart if Telecommunication enterprises presented a contented and reasonable price for its provided service, concealment of ADSL reseller profit reaping the end- user a triumph feeling, and an advantage-taken as a psychological gimmick applied by a united price of Telecommunication enterprises' service.

2. Results

Based on the data that was collected from the sample of the employee is working in / and customers are dealing with small and medium Internet distribution enterprises in the north of Upper Egypt about their perception about the impact of EUS on ADSL Telecommunication enterprises success.

The analysis began with the demographic profile of the respondents, such as gender, age, academic qualification, work experience, and enterprises. Second, an analysis of the survey questions related to respondent perceptions about their perception about affecting the success and EUS results according to the various research question and associated objective.

2.1 General Demographic Information

This section shows the background of the demographic data of the respondents who participate in this study, which is an essential and useful aspect to understand the data segmentation. The study used the fit-designed questionnaire as the best instrument. This was completed by the WOAM as well as the operator employee of the enterprises in the selected sector, above and beyond, another survey for the regional ADSL users who preferred due to its expected high response rate and oligopoly way that Telecommunication enterprises seems to behave. The two categories (ADSL users as well as Telecommunication enterprises staff, including the WOAMs) paved a way to detail's gathering and an interaction opportunity on the questions' answer. The first survey phase size was 150 of staff and WOAM concerning five ADSL Telecommunication enterprises at the north of Upper Egypt; a total of 71 completed questionnaires were received at a response rate of 47.3 %, which considered acceptable. The second survey targets 156, 000 of the whole population in the same region. The following sample show's characteristics in terms of the respondents (gender, age, academic qualification, work experience, and enterprises).

2.1.1 Descriptive Analysis

2.1.1.1 Gender

In the sample, there was 76.1 % male while 23.9 % female of ADSL Telecommunication enterprises individual respondents. Table 4.1 shows the demographic information about the gender. Actually, this percentage of respondents is revealing the Middle East culture which denotes men more likely to work rather than women. Demographic information about the gender is shown in table 2 and illustrated in figure 4.

Table 2. Gender

Valid	Frequency	Percent
Male	54	76.1
Female	17	23.9
Total	71	100.0

Figure 4. Gender

2.1.1.2 Age

The age of the respondents ranged respectively 8.5% less than 20 years, 22.5 % from 20-25, also 28.2 % form 26 -30, while 22.5 % from 31- 40, and 18.3 % more than 40 years old. This result reveals that majority of the respondents in this study was between age from 20- 40 year, which was more than 73 %, that means 73 % of the respondents were in youth age. Demographic information of the age is shown in table 3 and illustrated in figure 5.

Table 3. Age

Valid	Frequency	Percent
Less than 20 years	6	8.5
20-25 years	16	22.5
26 -30 years	20	28.2
30-40 years	16	22.5
More than 40 years	13	18.3
Total	71	100.0

Figure 5. Age

2.1.1.3 Academic Qualification:

The academic qualification of the respondents ranged respectively 12.7 % was a student, 29.6 % diploma, while 45.1 % bachelor's degree and 12.7 % were postgraduate. That means most of the respondents in this study were involving a high-level education. Demographic information of the academic qualification is shown in table 4 and illustrated in figure 6.

Table 4. Academic qualification

Valid	Frequency	Percent
Student	9	12.7
Diploma	21	29.6
Bachelor degree	32	45.1
Post graduate	9	12.7
Total	71	100.0

Figure 6. Academic qualification

2.1.1.4 Work Experience:

The work experience of the respondents ranged respectively, 32.4 less than 5 years, 42.3 from 6-10 years, and 25.4 more than 10 years, that high percentage of respondents who have experience from 5- 10 years, that obviously pertaining to the recentness of ADSL service industry that discovered only in nineties beginning as well as commercially in Egyptian market no more than two decades ago. Demographic information of the work experience is shown in table 5 and illustrated in figure 6.

Table 5. Work Experience

Valid	Frequency	Percent
Less than 5 Years	23	32.4
6-10 Years	30	42.3
More Than 10 Years	18	25.4
Total	71	100.0

Figure 7. Work Experience

2.1.1.5 Internet Distribution Enterprises

Regarding internet enterprises, the respondents were divide recording to five companies, Maidum Net, Data Lines, Turbo Net, Junior and Boraq Telecom. Table 4.5 reveals the companies of the respondents ranged respectively, 11.3 % from Maidum Net, 12.7 % from Data Lines, 7 % from Turbo Net, 21.1 % from Junior and 47.9 % from Boraq Telecom. This finding reveals that, high percentage of the respondents was from Boraq Telecom Company. Demographic information of the enterprises of the respondents is shown in table 6 and illustrated in figure 8.

Table 6. Internet distribution enterprises

Valid	Frequency	Percent
Maidum Net	8	11.3
Data Lines	9	12.7
Turbo Net	5	7
Junior	15	21.1
Boraq Telecom	34	47.9
Total	71	100.0

Figure 8. Internet distribution enterprises

2.2 Descriptive Statistics

2.2.1 Telecommunication enterprises Success:

Table 7 presents the distributions' responses on a perception of the WOAM and employees about their business, using 5-point Likert types ranging between (5) very successful and (1) very unsuccessful, Moreover, Table 4.9 presents the mean scores and standard deviation. Table 4.8 shows that overall; the mean score for the two statements is 3.86. The table shows that 35.2 % of the respondent was considering that their enterprises are very successful. On the other hand, no respondent was considering their enterprises are very unsuccessful. While 42.3 % of the respondent was considering they are successful relative to their competitors.

Table 7. Descriptive Statistics of success

	5	4	3	2	1	Mean	Std. D
Overall, how successful do you consider your business?	35.2%	32.4%	21.1%	11.3%	0%	3.91	1.0106
How successful do you consider your business relative to your competitors?	29.6%	42.3%	12.7%	11.3%	4.2%	3.81	1.1124
Total						3.86	

2.2.2 Customer Satisfaction:

Table 8 shows 51.8 % of respondents agreed to do the right thing when they decided to use the service of SME's, 49.1 % agreed to feel good about dealing with SME's, and 47.4 % agreed always delighted with the SME's service. The table shows that overall; the mean score for the three statements is 3.74.

Table 8. Descriptive Statistics of EUS

	5	4	3	2	1	Mean	Std. D
I am always delighted with the SME's service	20.2%	47.4%	19.3%	10.5%	2.6%	3.72	.991
I think I do the right thing when I decide to use the service of SME's	19.3%	51.8%	17.5%	7%	4.4%	3.75	.994
I feel good about using SME's	24.6%	49.1%	9.6%	11.4%	5.3%	3.76	1.108
Total						3.74	

2.3 Regression Analysis

2.3.1 Regression Analysis for the Relationship between EUS and Success

The results of regression analysis for the relationship between EUS and success are shown in the table 4.17.

Model 3

$$EUS = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SU + \epsilon$$

Where,

EUS: End-User Satisfaction

SU: Success

Table 9. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
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1	.517 ^a	.267	.256	1.51433
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a. Predictors: (Constant),

Table 10. ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	57.600	1	57.600	25.118	.000b
Residual	158.231	69	2.293		
Total	215.831	70			

a. Dependent Variable:

b. Predictors: (Constant),

Table 11. Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-2.001	2.046		-.978	.331
Success	.873	.174	.517	5.012	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Success

R² in the Table 4.17 indicates that independent variable (EUS) can explain 52 % of the variability in the dependent variable (success).

The Sig. in the ANOVA table, 4.18 is 0.000 (less than 0.05) which means that this model can highly significantly predict success, the Sig. in the coefficient, the table indicates that EUS has a significant influence on success.

B in coefficient Table 4.19 means the increment in "EUS" when a change is given to the independent variable. So, the B coefficient here shows that the EUS is positively affecting the "success."

2.4 Hypotheses Testing

- EUS will affect Telecommunication enterprises success.

The p-value (Sig.) for EUS was less than 0.05 (p = 0.000) which is highly significant, which means that EUS affects ADSL Telecommunication enterprises success. The B coefficient of EUS is 0.873, which means EUS can considerably positively affect ADSL Telecommunication enterprises success. Therefore, H4 is accepted.

3. Theorem

In this research, EUS are designated. It has been refined that customer service quality, practice experience, and pricing are most imperative factors in the researcher perception as well as referring to (Bowman and Narayandas, 2001).

4. Discussion

- Is end user satisfaction influence ADSL Telecommunication enterprises success?

Based on the study analysis, the EUS is being accepted as a mark of success. The research is being consistent with the findings of previous studies where the satisfaction level of "ETHIO

TELECOM" telecommunication internet customers affect success (AHMED, A. (2014). ADSL user is contemporary client mostly that when he convinced, the enterprise success will occur depending on levels of satisfaction (expectation, loyalty, and commitment). Success beyond satisfaction to accelerate provision advantage of customer delight to the company that its implementation and perform it well consistently" (Chandler, 1989, businesses now realize EUS as a primary goal on the path to profitability (Cronin and Taylor, 1992). The contribution of a satisfying user is also mentioned by Zekiri and Angelova (2011) who states that customer satisfaction effected positively on a firm profitability". Continuously, that customer satisfaction trailing the earnings positive impact (O'Sullivan & McCallig (2012).

4.1 Implication of the Study

4.1.1 Empirical Implications

Findings from this study will evaluate academicians in broadening of the prospectus with respect to this study, hence providing a deeper understanding of measuring success and EUS as a new discipline comes up with user manners and Telecommunication enterprises WOAM internal factors' scaled concerns.

An Integrated and comprehensive approach has been led the study towards practical results.

4.1.2 Practical Implications

EUS is a momentous factor impacting the success, the significance of the impact of satisfaction that customers are likely to switch ADSL Telecommunication enterprises distribution brand directly in response to deteriorating satisfaction. Eventually, satisfaction roles of users are suggested as follow;

Absorption of frontline personnel that facilitates social interactions with target customers, exchange views on any concern information and bearing other departments' drawbacks are the prime assignment.

Accordingly, ADSL Resellers have to strongly emphasize market surveys of the satisfaction of customers, as subjective acuties of ADSL distributors do not suffice to clarify the views of customers in this area.

Reputation of ADSL Telecommunication enterprises experience causes users to determine norms, which avail as frames of reference for judging satisfaction as well as it could be accredited through users' training within troubleshooting programs. Additionally, monitor customers' perceptions for continuous improvement has conceptualized the word of mouth broadcast.

Escalation is the users' right, in turn, the WOAM should take his responsibility to resolve any internal/external problem personally by facing customers in person, competent and senior staff are not only likely to be able to resolve the problem promptly, nevertheless will also have more power to bid compensation for any inconvenience or other loss experienced by customers that emotionally pertain as well as revealing the critical message of a future crisis, due to the poor selling's behaviours of an unqualified liaison.

4.1.3 Policy Implications

Accordingly, obligatory governmental license and educational condition are most suggested to generate a pattern of nascent entrepreneur as regard of education singe that affect especially hi-tech service Telecommunication enterprises success accordance with result of this study.

EUS as a most significant impact of the study calls for placing an integrated program of Telecommunication enterprises service quality-duty and end-user right jointly.

Establishing and launching a public database on Telecommunication enterprises favour availability of statistics and appropriate data to facilitate EUS market research and study.

4.2 Recommendation

This study attempted to assess the impact of EUS on ADSL Telecommunication enterprises in the north of Upper Egypt with a few limitations. Typically, EUSs pre/post act-time, satisfaction levels, and user's categories/niche market etc. are differentiated for several perceptions regard to nature of things. Fragmentation is the trait of those studies attribution to social, economic, political, and experiential factors that control the research results. Understanding, comparison, and compromising these researchers are worthwhile to master the conceptual perception of the researcher.

The scope of the place; (north of Upper Egypt), could be represent other regional sectors, whole country, and even the characteristic developing countries at the same conditions. In addition, study has been conducted in one particular service industry (ADSL service) in a single-country setting (North of Upper Egypt). As a result, the generalizability of the findings might be limited. Consequently, additional researches across different industries and countries will be required in order to generalize the findings.

This study already has currently, conducted in ADSL Telecommunication enterprises might other researches discuss the future of ADSL service especially, it does not exist utterly, Three decades ago as a telecommunication applicable commercial service.

Viability, availability, and possibility are somewhat hurdles of this research. Telecommunication enterprises are variously assorted with accordance of a product/service character in each industry; in particular, ADSL as internet service is a unique Telecommunication enterprises type, a user's overall evaluation of ADSL service based on the judgment of cost and benefit is not an entirely cognitive tradeoff between perceptions of duties and rights.

Regardless of the study lengthy period and a huge effort, it would be possible to recognize a sort of Telecommunication enterprises that responsible of providing spectacular service in this era "the internet service distribution". Future researchers can take note of these shortcomings in planning future research work.

5. Research Methodology

Investigate the EUS direct impact on ADSL Telecommunication enterprises success in Egypt.

Figure 9. Research Methodology

6. Hypothesis Development

Subsequent to the research objectives the following hypotheses were formulated for the purposes of it. It should be distinguished that these research hypotheses are analyzed and discussed according to each of their various biographical details.) EUS affecting Telecommunication enterprises success. (Huang, X., Soutar, G. N., & Brown, A: 2004), (Ismail Salaheldin, S: 2009).

Telecommunication enterprises ADSL broadband access, quality, and stability. In other words, consumers are likely to consider both customer service features (i.e. employee's professionals,

attitude and interesting) and ADSL features (i.e. speed browsing, downloads ability, transmission quality and stability).

These hypotheses were generated assuming the literature review and prior to the identification of the research population and sample. Conducted hypotheses of that mentioned below are based on the fact that at this point in the research process, the population was not clearly identified and the sample not yet taken. Explanatory studies are built on exploratory research and endeavor to validate the factors why something occurs (Neuman, 2003). This is the characteristic of an elucidative study. Exploratory study; where the researcher is trying to find out what is happening to seek new insights, to ask questions and access phenomena in a brand-new light (Robson, 1993). This research is an Explanatory study, on the other hand, looks at the relationship between variables. A situation is studied in order to explain the relationship between the variables. In this particular research, descriptive study is used since we are not very sure of the answers, and explanatory will be used to determine the relationship between customer service, , EUS that supposed to affect ADSL Telecommunication enterprises success either positively or negatively.

- H: EUS will affect Telecommunication enterprises success.

Research design is the outline for achieving research objectives and answering research questions. It is defined as a strategic plan to execute a research study (William, G. Z. (2003). ADSL Telecommunication enterprises EUS variable supposed to affect a success variable independently. The interference variables will not be used throughout this study. There will be some autonomous in the independent and dependent variables. Conversely, all targeted ADSL Telecommunication enterprises in the specific region is conducted to examine the relationship nature among dissembler variables.

6.1 Measurement of Variables/Instrumentation

Quantitative research Bryman & Bell (2011) define research strategy as “a general orientation to the conduct of business research” (Ibid). The questionnaire was designed predominantly by the researcher following the principal literature review and corresponding theories, and partially adapted from an existing questionnaire (Du, S., Keil, M., Mathiassen, L., Shen, Y., & Tiwana, A. (2007)). This concerned the success of ADSL Telecommunication enterprises’ internal factors and EUS relationships. The research survey is conducted in two phases.

First survey phase, have three sections, Sections A refer to the interference variables employed to hold that are: age, gender, qualification, and the employee experience period in the identified Telecommunication enterprises. Degree Age has been divided into four phases, Age in five levels above 35 and below than 20 years old, Gender includes male and female. Academic Qualification including Degrees from diploma to PhD. Prior Experience period have been spent at the quantified Telecommunication enterprises.

Second survey phase concern the EUS refer to age and gender information and ADSL TELECOMMUNICATION ENTERPRISES subscription. As well as Section B refining to satisfaction extension of the user in overall 5 questions about the ADSL TELECOMMUNICATION ENTERPRISES distributor. Likert scale ranging from one (1: Strongly disagree), (2: Disagree), (3: Neutral), (4: Agree) and (5: Strongly agree) was applied to measure the ADSL responses. Again last two questions about competition situation to measure his hopes and reflect his loyalty. The questioner question conducted regarding to reviews of (TJ Brown, JC Mowen, DT Donovan: 2002), (Mithas, S., Krishnan, M. S., & Fornell, C. (2005), (Levesque, T., & McDougall, G. H.:1996), (Huang, X., Soutar, G. N., & Brown, A: 2004), (Ismail Salaheldin, S: 2009). The use of quantitative research was measured to collect and analyses data. Questionnaires are used and data are standardized, it is easily understood and easy to compare.

The second survey phase carried out to investigate if the subscribers’ satisfaction for the same Telecommunication enterprises would be affected ADSL Telecommunication enterprises success. The research made use of a research instrument similar to conducted study of (Chloe Wilmot, 2012).

Section C referring to the staff, WOAM impression and perception an about his/her TELECOMMUNICATION ENTERPRISES success. That carried out with a five point Likert scale ranging from one (1: Strongly disagree), (2: Disagree), (3; Neutral), (4: Agree) and (5: Strongly agree) referring to measuring an affective variables, given that they allow researchers to gather large amounts of data with relative ease (Nemoto, T., & Beglar, D. (2014).

6.2 Data Collection

6.2.1 Sources of Data

The research labored both primary and secondary sources of data collection.

- Primary Sources

In order to comprehend the objective, the study used the fit-designed questionnaire as the best instrument. This was completed by the WOAM as well as an operator employee of ADSL Telecommunication enterprises in the selected region. Besides, another survey for ADSL users preferred due to its high response rate as well as a worrying approach that ADSL Telecommunication enterprises seems to behave. That confer the two categories (ADSL Users, Telecommunication enterprises staff, including the WOAM) concerned an opportunity to interact and get details on the questions and answers through the dual questionnaire. Clarify issues easily; it achieves and leads to an accuracy of data from the respondents.

- Sampling

Telecommunication enterprises end user as well as employee and WOAM in North or Upper Egypt as of the beginning of 2017. A random method is a sample selected in such a way that every possible sample of the same size is equally likely to be chosen, exactly, as conducted for ADSL users' survey as well as the staff and WOAM referring to the fame of five ADSL Telecommunication enterprises at the identical region. In addition, the first survey phase size was 150 of staff and WOAM concerning the fame of five ADSL Telecommunication enterprises in the north of Upper Egypt. Purposive samplings are run of users' survey targeted around 4% out of, altogether, ADSL users who are 3.9 million ADSL modem subscribers, in the Arab Republic of Egypt referring to The Ministry of Communications and Information Technology (MCIT) report in January 2017, That result in, the second survey target disproportionately 156,000 of whole the same regional population. Additionally, the study utilized sectional in the sense that all relevant data were collected at a single online point in time. The reason for favoring a cross-sectional study is due to constraints of time and money. And obtaining information from a cross-section of a population at a single point in time is a reasonable strategy for pursuing many descriptive pieces of research (Janet M. Ruane, 2006).

6.3 Data Collection Procedure

In this research, a mixture of convenience sampling and purposive sampling are used.

The use of convenience sampling in this study was based on practical reasons. Descriptive pieces of research (Janet M. Ruane, 2006). Firstly, the researcher's hometown is North of Upper Egypt region; he got merit of access to the Telecommunication enterprises and was also partially acquainted with several of the participants of ADSL Telecommunication enterprises staff and much more less of ADSL end users. Secondly, no sampling frame which is "an accurate, complete listing of all the elements among the population" (Hair et al., 2003) was found to exist.

Both questionnaires were being conducted online as regards with the targeted slice. The first survey phase was carried out for the staff, owners or/ managers of five well-known small and medium enterprises in an ADSL distribution field through online emails that had sent to them after owner's permission. The record central stipulation since Telecommunication enterprises cannot employ more than fifty full-time paid employees, irrespective of the sector, (Egyptian law of small establishment's number 141 for the year 2004). Second survey phase was for general ADSL users in the particular area; north of Upper Egypt through a commercial Compiegne among Facebook users, that determined the interests of users and geographic area to be more precise, and sending emails for acquainted subscribers on the aimed region.

The SPSS was used in order to answer the research questions.

7. Operational Definition

'Enterprise': It refers to a unit of economic organization or activity, whether public or private engaged into the manufacturing of goods.

'Respondent': respondents are those individuals who are owner/managers/ staff of an enterprise and ADSL end-user.

'ADSL' means Asymmetric Digital Subscriber Line.

'ISP' means Internet Service Provider licensed to provide access to Internet Service

'License' means a license granted by the Agency under which a service is provided by an operator, whereas a 'Licensee' means an operator that is licensed to provide Internet Services.

'Broadband' is defined as "An always-on data connection that is able to support interactive services including Internet access and has the capability of the minimum download speed of 256 kilobits per second (kbps) to an individual subscriber from the Internet node of the service provider

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